

THE METHODS AND FUNCTIONS OF TRANSLATING RELIGIOUS TEXTS

Abduvaliyeva Farangizxon Salohiddin qizi

Student of Fergana State University

Baxtiyorovafarangiz9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT. *The study of the religious texts translation is much more difficult when compared with other types of translational works. While translating them we have to compare not only history, but also culture of all religious texts. This diversity is able to help to differentiate each of them. Additionally, in translation of religious texts we can use number of methods and functions to delineate them obviously to others. Due to the fact that the books are not the original literal books, so they made holy by God. In fact, With the exception of slight variations in the pronunciation of vowels and punctuation, Dr. Daniel Brubaker has created a series of videos that he refers to as the "Version of the Qur'an" that detail the additions, modifications, and alterations made to the original Qur'anic texts. [2] and The Qur'an has been translated into more than 1000 languages. After the independence of Uzbekistan, Alouddin Mansur's book "The Holy Qur'an" with annotated Uzbek translation (Tashkent, 1991) was published.*

KEY WORDS: *translation, translator, holy books, audiovisual, imitation, transcription, religious, culture, islam, Christ.*

INTRODUCTION

The origins of religious translation can be found in the translation of biblical books. Translations including theology or other processes involving languages of religion subsequently became more widespread and commonplace. Therefore, the first religious translations were restricted to holy books like the Bible. According to Naudé (2010), the Bible was first translated at least 200 BCE. Naturally, there

were many challenges along the way, ranging from issues with provenance to the inherent difficulty of comparability. Naudé (2010) clarifies that whereas completing the translation of the Bible was a major undertaking, the translation of the al-Qur'an was not. The investigation of translation now include audiovisual translation as a core component. The terms "audiovisual" and "translation" need to be clarified here. Translation, also known as is an approach of converting text from one source language to another target language, according to academic consensus. Various academics employ different terms to describe the process of change, such as "rendering" for Newmark and "reproducing" for Nida (Yinhua, 2011). Any word will nonetheless, nevertheless, deal with the process of translating text between languages. This instance of translation is focused on the audiovisual text, which is made up of several channels and symbols. The shift in linguistic translation of audio according to Chaume (2013), is affecting semiotic propagation as well as the linguistic continuum. As a result, audiovisual translation is an increasingly complicated entity than written text since it involves lexical aspects, symbols, and signs. The translation of audiovisual content includes dubbing and subtitling, for instance. The primary distinction between subtitling and dubbing is the goal outcome's mode shift. While in subtitling the source language is in the form of printed matter and the language being targeted is in the form of speech, in dubbing both the source and target languages are speech-based. researchers have studied translation techniques in great detail. There are two methods that are commonly used in the study of audiovisual translation: Gottlieb's Subtitling Strategies (Gottlieb, 1992); and Molina and Albir Translation Revisited (Molina & Albir, 2002). The strategies in Gottlieb's Subtitling Strategies consist of ten strategies that directly focus on how the subtitles are displayed, focusing more on the technical captioning procedures. Depending on the text, the tactics discussed include decimation, condensation, paraphrase, resignation, deletion, expansion, dislocation, imitation, transcription, and transfer. An example of a study using this approach is

by Khasanah and Nugrahaeni (2021).

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Translating religious texts presents a set of unique challenges due to the complexity of religious language, cultural nuances, and the importance of maintaining the integrity and accuracy of the original text. Here are some methods and functions commonly used in translating religious texts:

1. **Literal Translation:** This method aims to reproduce the original text word-for-word, focusing on maintaining the most accurate translation possible. It is typically employed when the text contains specific theological or doctrinal concepts that need to be accurately conveyed.

2. **Dynamic Equivalence:** Dynamic equivalence focuses on conveying the meaning of the text rather than a literal translation. It aims to capture the essence, intent, and impact of the original text while utilizing language and cultural expressions that resonate with the target audience. This approach is commonly used when translating religious texts aimed at a broader or non-native audience.

3. **Formal Equivalence:** Also known as "faithful" or "functional" equivalence, this method aims to maintain both the form and function of the original text. It seeks to reproduce the grammar, syntax, and idiomatic expressions of the source text as closely as possible, while also capturing its intended meaning.

4. **Contextualization:** Contextualization involves adjusting the translation according to the target culture's religious and cultural context, customs, and beliefs. It aims to make the translated text more relatable and accessible to the audience, employing culturally specific terms, idioms, and concepts.

5. **Interlinear Translation:** This method involves providing a literal translation of each word or phrase directly below the source text. It is commonly used in scholarly or academic settings to aid in understanding the original language and syntax while providing a direct, word-for-word translation.

6. **Exegetical and Hermeneutical Considerations:** Translating religious texts often

requires deep knowledge of both the source and target languages, as well as the associated religious and theological concepts. Translators may need to interpret difficult passages or ambiguous terms based on historical context, religious understanding, and textual analysis.

7. Cultural Adaptation: When translating religious texts, cultural adaptation is often necessary to ensure the text resonates with the target audience. This may involve replacing or adding religious expressions, rituals, or practices familiar to the target culture while maintaining the original spiritual or doctrinal meaning.

8. Glossaries and Footnotes: Complex religious texts may require the inclusion of glossaries or footnotes to provide explanations, definitions, or alternative interpretations of key terms, concepts, or cultural references. These aids can enhance the reader's understanding and engagement with the translated religious text.

9. Collaborative Approaches: Translating religious texts often benefits from collaboration among scholars, theologians, linguists, and native speakers of the target language. This collaborative effort brings together different areas of expertise, ensuring a more accurate and culturally appropriate translation.

10. Review and Quality Assurance: Translation of religious texts should undergo rigorous review and quality assurance processes to ensure fidelity to the source text and adherence to the intended meaning. Reviewers may include experts in the source and target languages, religious scholars, and members of the faith community to ensure accuracy and faithfulness.

In summary, translating religious texts requires a combination of linguistic expertise, theological knowledge, cultural understanding, and sensitivity to the intended audience. The methods and functions employed may vary according to the specific religious tradition, text, and target audience.

Meyer introduced four fundamental purposes of humor in communication by using a communicative method based on the genesis of humor: two that bring

communicators together (identification and clarification) and two that set one group of communicators apart from another. Identification is the use of self-deprecating humor to make allies with the audience (Chapter 1978), whereas clarity aids communicators in summarizing and presenting their arguments. You laugh with others in both situations.

Undoubtedly, culture presents one of the most challenging subjects for translators to work with because it can lead to a number of issues during the translation process, including issues with idioms and metaphors, forms of address, and issues with words that have dual meanings. The notion of culture is essential to any translation methodology. Translations into foreign languages always involve intercultural communication because culture is a key component of translation. An important error will be made by the translator if they fail to recognize the relationship between language and culture. There are some important sites of translating most popular religious books from target language to source language. It is clear that Quran and Bible are the most renowned ones among translation world because of their popularity

The importance of translation to Christianity has been emphasized by Lamin O. Sanneh (1990). If not for the need to communicate essential Christian ideas to a wide range of cultural groups in numerous languages, Catholicism might not have fled Palestine. There are four Great Ages in the history of Bible translation progress. The First Great Age (c. a period of 200 to 4 CE) was a Jewish period in Western Asia and Alexandria, with Greek and Aramaic serving as the target languages. Palestine and the burgeoning Christian communities throughout the territory of the Roman Empire served as the primary hubs of the Catholic Second Great Age, which spanned from the fourth century CD to around 1500, often known as the Middle/Dark Ages. Latin, or Jerome's Vulgate, was the language of intent. Throughout the translation process, there was a clear commitment to the outdated vocabulary and style as well as the word-for-word replacement concept. The

character of the translated works was an attempt to preserve the nutrients such as macro and substructure and forms of the original text. The source text's rational purposes were not given much thought. The King James Version or Authorized Version, the American Standard Version, the Dutch Authorized Version, and others are well-known translations from this era.

Ismatulla Abdullayev who was a renowned Arabic scholar, translated this text into Uzbek Cyrillic in 2012 at his own expense and 100 copies were published. Important information on the history of translations, the translation, and the life and work of Oltinkhan Tora was included in his prelude to the Qur'an in Uzbek. Published by Ismatulla Abdullayev, this translation solely includes the original Altinkhan Tora text."Tafsiri Hilal" is translated to match the verses exactly and provides an explanation of them. Additionally, a large amount of room is given to the remarks in Alauddin Mansur's translation. Below are the initial recommendations:

1. The words are accurately translated, and the only thing God himself displays in them is what you have written. Reviews, remarks, and statements are not included.

2. It is imperative that remarks be made, assertions be made. so long as they don't take excessive action. However, it is distinct in its own right to offer The 2001 edition lists it on a different page.A few brief remarks are made. However, they fall short. There have been so many revolutions that realities remain unexplained.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, translations of the Qur'an for the benefit of people who could not read the original were not encouraged by Islam. Conversely, some Muslim officials even denounced as impious or even blasphemous the attempt to create such translations. Thus, the Qur'anic translation is a controlled translation. Rigorous restrictions on whose expertise converts, what gets translated, the manner in which it is interpreted, for whomever the phenomenon is translated, and how regularly the

outcome of the translation is distributed and debated are all part of controlled translation, as defined by Robinson (2000: 103–107). In relation to Bible translation Religious history indicates that common people want and receive translations of religious writings into their own tongues. Pentateuch for the Hellenized Jewish community in Memphis and Latina for the Latin-speaking followers of Christ of the fourth and fifth centuries are two examples of this. The control over the translation's comprehensibility is reminiscent of the previous Bible translations from the evangelical societies' era. This leads to a literal translation that maintains the sacred text's integrity.

REFERENCES

1. M.A.Mahmoud// Problems of Translating Islamic Religious Items-Beirut,2014.
2. J.A.Naude//Religious translation- University of Free State, 2010
3. I.G'ofurov,N.Qambarova,O.Mo'minov//Tarjima nazariyasi-Toshkent, 2012
4. Ubaydullaeva, Durdon, and Muhammadjon Tojiboyev. "TRANSLATION IS THE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC AND LITERARY." Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2023.
5. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ҚЎШМА ГАПЛАР ТАВСИФИ, ТАСНИФИ ВА МЕТАТИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. Science and innovation, 1(Б6), 560-564.
6. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOLOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 560-564.
7. Ubaydullaeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA IJTIMOY YO'NALISHNING TARAQQIYOTI. Science and innovation, 1(Б6), 869-873.
8. G'opporova, N., & Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). A COMMUNICATIVE PRAGMATIC STUDY OF MEANS OF EXPRESSING DIRECTIVE SPEECH

ACTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 825-827.

9. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL DIRECTION IN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 869-873.
10. Gulyora, A., Odina, A., Asadbek, A., & Durdona, A. (2023). LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC TRANSFORMATION IN WRITTEN TRANSLATION. "RUSSIAN" ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ, 9(1).
11. Kamolaxon, A., Shahina, A., Nodiraxon, A., & Gavharoy, A. (2023). TRANSLATION OF PHRASES AND TERMS RELATED TO INTERNATIONAL AND INTERSTATE POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS. DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY", 14(1).
12. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Qayumova, S. (2022). O'zbek Xalq Maqollarining O'zbek Folklorshunosligida O'rganilishi. Miasto Przyszłości, 30, 133-134.
13. Sarvinoz, X., Nigora, O., Azima, S., & Marhabo, O. (2023, May). FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATOR'S STYLE IN POETIC TRANSLATION. In "CANADA" INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DEVELOPMENTS IN EDUCATION, SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (Vol. 9, No. 1).
14. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOLOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Science and Innovation, 1(6), 560-564.
15. Ubaydullaeva, D., & Yuldasheva, Z. (2020). POLYSEMY IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. In АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ (pp. 234-235)